

Single Atom Engineered Antibiotics Overcome Bacterial Resistance

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Abstract:

A class of antibiotics are developed with the potential to bypass bacterial resistance. [1]. By leveraging single atom engineering, we embedded manganese into a covalently modified graphene, yielding a material capable of targeting and eliminating a broad spectrum of bacterial pathogens, including multidrug-resistant strains from the ESCAPE group. The material exerts its antimicrobial activity by chemically attacking carbohydrates in bacterial cell walls, a mechanism that disrupts key physiological

functions and prevents resistance development. This innovative approach enables potent bactericidal action at low, non-toxic concentrations.

In vivo studies on mouse models demonstrated rapid and effective healing of skin infections caused by resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, highlighting its therapeutic promise for localized applications such as wound dressings or antimicrobial coatings on medical devices. The findings mark a significant advance in the fight against antibiotic resistance and underscore the transformative potential of single atom engineered materials in modern medicine.

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